

FISCAL POLICY VARIABLES AND MANUFACTURING SECTOR PERFORMANCE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: Governments across the world developed policies, including fiscal policies aimed at attracting investments to the manufacturing sector, as fiscal policies are major determinants of manufacturing performance. Thus, this study investigated the impact of fiscal policy variables on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria from 1986 to 2023 using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Regression technique. Results revealed that government tax revenue is positively and significantly related to manufacturing sector performance in the short-run. Similarly, over the long term, the projected impact of government tax revenue on manufacturing sector performance is positive but statistically insignificant. On the other hand, the findings indicated that government recurrent expenditure affected manufacturing sector performance negatively in the short-run. However, government recurrent expenditure is positively and insignificantly related to manufacturing sector performance in the long run. Furthermore, the estimated impact of one period lagged government capital expenditure on manufacturing sector performance in the short-run is positive and significant. While, government capital expenditure is insignificant and negatively related to manufacturing sector performance in the long run. While, the coefficient of external debts at level is positive and significant in the short run. However, external debt is negative and insignificantly related to manufacturing sector performance in the long-run. This study therefore recommended that the Federal Ministry of Finance in collaboration with the Federal Inland Revenue Service should enhance efficiency in tax administration and widen the tax net to include the informal sector and digital economy. Further, the Budget Office of the Federation, and National Assembly Appropriations Committee should reallocate recurrent expenditure towards sectors that directly support the manufacturing sector (e.g., energy subsidies, transportation, R&D support). Also, the Federal Ministry of Works and Housing, and Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission should improve the planning, execution, and monitoring of capital projects, ensuring they target manufacturing-enabling infrastructure. While, the Debt Management Office, Ministry of Finance, National Assembly should limit unproductive external borrowing by tying new external borrowing strictly to capital projects that directly enhance industrial productivity (e.g., industrial parks, power generation).

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the manufacturing sub-sector serves as a fundamental pillar of economic expansion,

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driving industrialization, creating employment opportunities, and fostering innovation. While, fiscal policy plays a critical role in shaping the performance of the manufacturing sector with two broad strategies adopted by governments across the globe. One of the strategies adopted by governments globally is demand-side fiscal interventions, which focus on stimulating demand for manufactured goods through increased government spending, consumer tax cuts, and direct subsidies. The second strategies adopted by governments is supply-side fiscal interventions, which aim to enhance production capacity, improve efficiency, and promote industrial competitiveness through tax incentives, infrastructure investment, and research & development (R&D) support. However, the effectiveness of these interventions varies across economies, depending on factors such as macroeconomic conditions, industrial structure, and policy execution. For example, many governments stimulus packages during economic downturns (e.g., COVID-19) have mixed effects on manufacturing depending on allocation and implementation efficiency., as some of the fiscal policies support short-term recovery but may not lead to long-term manufacturing growth (Guerrieri *et al.*, 2020).

Some of the best practices in terms of fiscal policy interventions from successful economies globally are China combined demand-side stimulus (infrastructure projects) with supply-

side industrial policies (subsidies for high-tech manufacturing) (World Bank, 2019), Germany supply-side interventions through industrial policies, skilled labour development, and R&D incentives (Audretsch & Elston, 2017), and the United States stimulus checks boosting demand (COVID-19 response) and corporate tax cuts encouraging investment (Zidar, 2019). As part of fiscal policy intervention, the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act (ARRA) of 2009 injected \$787 billion into the economy, increasing demand for manufacturing inputs, with an estimated fiscal multiplier of 1.5 (Ramey, 2019). Similarly, the UK's "Super-Deduction" (2021-2023) allowed firms to deduct 130% of investment costs, boosting manufacturing investment (IMF, 2022). While, China's "Made in China 2025" strategy provides subsidies for advanced manufacturing sectors, boosting global competitiveness (Wübbecke *et al.*, 2016).

With escalating global and domestic challenges, the growth of the Nigerian manufacturing sector has been hampered, resulting in its underperformance when compared to other countries which has made it evidently necessary to reassess growth strategies within the sector, and resolve critical concerns (KPMG, 2023). Specifically, the performance of the Nigerian manufacturing sector has not been impressive, as the share of manufacturing in the country's aggregate output remains stuck at the very low levels. For example, the contribution of the

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sector to GDP growth fell from 8.3 to 3.4 percent between 1993 and 2001. These provided strong evidence that the manufacturing industry in Nigeria has been dwindling. While, between 2002 and 2007, the manufacturing share in GDP growth witnessed only a marginal increase of 3.0 percent. A decline was again recorded in 2008 and 2009 but there was a consistent upward trend of 7% in 2010 to 10 percent in 2014 which however declined drastically to 3.2% in 2015 at the beginning of the 2014 economic recession. However, manufacturing share in GDP slipped into negative in 2016 at -0.8% at the peak of the crisis but rose incredibly in 2017 to 11.4% and 19.4% in 2018 (Central Bank of Nigeria, [CBN], 2019). The growth of the manufacturing sector has been weak and sluggish since its recovery from the Covid-19 Pandemic with an average annual growth of 3.4% in 2021 and 2.5% in 2022, culminating in the sector's contribution to Nigeria's GDP falling far short of globally competitive levels, averaging 10% in its annual contribution to GDP in almost two decades (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2023).

In the past, the government has intervened through various policies to improve manufacturing capacity, generates employment, and distributes income. The policy response aimed at dealing with persistent underperformance of the manufacturing sector has taken several forms such as the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986; the

Export Promotion Industrialization Strategy (EPI) in 1986; the Trade and Financial Liberalization Policy in 1989; Establishment of the Bank of Industry (BOI) in 2000 and the Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS) in 2000. A more recent policy effort aimed at improving the country's manufacturing sector performance was the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) which covered the period 2017-2020. It was a medium-term plan designed to revive the Nigerian economy from the 2014- 2016 economic recession.

Despite the cumulative policy efforts, the performance of the Nigerian manufacturing sector has not been impressive, as the share of manufacturing in the country's aggregate output remains stuck at the very low levels. The persistent underperformance of the manufacturing sector in defiance of all revitalizing policy efforts motivated this paper to examine the impact of fiscal policy variables on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria from 1986 to 2023.

METHODOLOGY

Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have been carried out on the impact of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector performance. This paper therefore reviews some of this works with focus on currency, relevance and appropriateness of empirical studies as follows:

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Edeh and Okia (2024) examined the impact of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria for the period (1981-2021). To analyse the data, the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique was used. The results showed that government expenditure has positive and significant impact on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. Based on the findings, it is recommended that government should enhance its revenue base by diversifying its revenue sources, this can be done by increasing the amount of money invested in other sectors of the economy by 30 percent such as agricultural sector, tourism, etc.

Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, Effiong *et al.* (2024) explored the influence of fiscal policy (government expenditure and taxation) and interest rate on the manufacturing sector of the Nigerian economy for the period 1981 to 2021. Findings of the study indicated that in the short run, government expenditure and its one-period lag exerted a negative and significant influence on manufacturing sector performance; value added tax exerted a positive and significant effect on manufacturing sector performance while its one-period lag exerted a negative and significant effect; and interest rate exerted a positive and significant effect on manufacturing sector performance. In the long run, government expenditure put forth a negative but insignificant effect on manufacturing sector performance; while value added tax and interest

rate exert positive and significant effect. The study recommended that there is need for a reduction in the cost of governance as a huge proportion of public spending is used in running the government other than being utilized in stirring critical sectors that could stir manufacturing sector performance.

Joshua-Gyang (2024) examined the impact of fiscal policy on manufacturing industrial sector in Nigeria from 1987 to 2022. The study adopted the Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach and found that the coefficient of the government capital expenditures, oil taxation and public external debt have a negative effect on manufacturing industrial output. While, government recurrent expenditures, non-oil taxation and public domestic debt were found to have a positive effect on manufacturing industrial output. Therefore, the government through the Federal Ministry of Finance and other related Agencies should design a mechanism to track the fiscal policy indicators in Nigeria to ensure that projects are industrially driven, especially the infrastructural projects for a massive increase in manufacturing industrial output in Nigeria.

Alugbuo *et al.* (2023) investigated the impact of fiscal policy, automatic stabilizers on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria for the period 1981-2022. The ARDL estimation technique was used for estimation. Results showed that total government expenditure had negative relationship with manufacturing sector

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output in the short-run while in the long-run, it had positive relationship with manufacturing sector output; Tax revenue had negative relationship with manufacturing sector output in the current year and significantly contributed to manufacturing sector performance in the previous years; gross fixed capital formation had positive and insignificant relationship with manufacturing sector output in the current year at 5% level of significance. The study recommended among others that government should increase and channel spending to capital projects and social overheads that will encourage private sector investment.

Chukwuka *et al.* (2023) examined the implication of the fiscal policy response on the Nigeria manufacturing sector growth between 1980 and 2021. The study utilized Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL). Results revealed that fiscal policy which was proxied by government expenditure had a positive relationship between manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria but at a very meagre significant level. The study recommended a strong fiscal policy formulation that will revamp the manufacturing sector through infrastructure development, granting of interest free credit facilities, good roads, and protection from heavy exploitation by unfavourable exchange rates.

Alozie (2021) examined the impact of fiscal policy on the real sectors performance in Nigeria between 1981 and 2018. The Autoregressive Distribution Lag (Short-run and Long-run

ARDL) econometric methodology was adopted. The study found out that while government expenditure positively and significantly impacted on the performance of the agricultural contribution to GDP and industrial contribution to GDP; Tax revenue also had an impact on the performance of agricultural and industrial sector contribution to GDP. Furthermore. In the short run ARDL both AGDP and INGDP, capital expenditure (CEX) was statistically significant. While in the long run ARDL for AGDP, CEX and TAX were significant, meaning an increase in capital expenditure (CEX) and TAX will lead to a potential increase in the Agricultural contribution to GDP (AGDP). In the long run ARDL for INGDP. Capital expenditure (CEX) and re-current expenditure (REX) was statistically significant, meaning an increase in capital expenditure (CEX) and re-current expenditure (REX) will lead to a potential increase in the Industrial contribution to GDP (INGDP). The study recommended that an expansionary fiscal policy (i.e increase in government spending should be implemented) in the real sectors and contractionary fiscal policy (i.e reduction in tax levies) should be implemented in the real sectors.

Ubesie *et al.* (2020) examined the potential of fiscal policy to stimulate manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. The model estimation employed the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique, while the effect of estimation was carried out using the Granger

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causality test. The result of the analysis revealed that recurrent expenditure has no significant effect on manufacturing sector performance. However, capital expenditure, fiscal deficit, and the company's income tax significantly affect manufacturing sector performance. The study recommended that the Federal, State and Local governments should stop wasteful expenditure on unnecessary meetings, seminars, workshops, foreign trips, etc. to increase spending on basic industrial infrastructures, most importantly on the power supply and road network to stimulate the manufacturing sector performance.

Ubong and Ettah (2020) investigated the influence of government expenditure on industrial sector output of Nigeria for the period 1980 to 2018. Government expenditure was disaggregated into capital and recurrent expenditures. Vector Error Correction (VEC) model was used to estimate both the short-run and long-run estimates. Findings from the VEC revealed that both government capital and recurrent expenditures significantly influences industrial output in the short-run. Also, capital expenditure does not have a significant relationship with industrial sector output in the long-run but recurrent expenditure does. The study recommended that concerted efforts should be made on the part of the government to boost the industrial sector output through development of the nation's infrastructural facilities, in other to encourage domestic

investors and win more foreign investors which are highly competitive globally.

Ajudua and Imoisi (2018) investigated the nexus between fiscal policy and the Nigeria manufacturing sector output. Employing the Error Correction Model (ECM) method, time series data for the period 1986-2016 were tested to ascertain the relationship between manufacturing sector output (dependent variable) and three independent variables. Findings from the study established that government expenditure was significant and positively related to manufacturing sector output in Nigeria while government revenue was not significant. The study recommended expansionary fiscal policy measures, diversification of the economy to enhance the performance of manufacturing sector, improved allocation to the manufacturing sector during budget implementation so as to increase the sector performance.

Bolakale (2018) examined the impact of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector outputs in Nigeria and utilized Manufacturing sector outputs (MSO) as explained variable, while Government Expenditure (GXP) and Government Tax Revenue (GTR) as explanatory variables. Other variables such as interest rate, savings rate, foreign exchange rate are control variables, the study employed Ordinary Least Squares and ARDL techniques to analyze the relationship. The study found that government expenditure and tax revenue have positive

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relation to manufacturing sector outputs in Nigeria but the tax revenue is not statistically significant. In the long run but fiscal policies (government expenditure and tax revenue) are statistically significant. The study recommended that government expenditures should be used in critical productive areas, and imposes optimal tax on incomes of companies.

Ezejiofor *et al.* (2015) assessed whether tax as a fiscal policy tool affects the performance of the selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria using descriptive method and data were collected through the use of six years of financial accounts of the selected companies. The study found that taxation as a fiscal policy instrument has a significant effect on the performance of Nigerian manufacturing companies. Based on the findings, it was recommended, among other things, that the government is required to be sensitive to the variables in the tax environment and other macro-environmental factors to enable the manufacturing sector to cope with the ever-changing dynamics of the manufacturing environment.

In the same vein, Uzoka and Eze (2015) examined the effect of government capital expenditure on the manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. They used quantitative time series data and multiple regression techniques in the analysis. The result revealed that capital expenditure on road infrastructure and telecommunication affects the manufacturing sector output in Nigeria significantly while

government capital expenditure on power has an insignificant effect on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. The study recommended that there is need for government to reduce its budgetary allocation to recurrent expenditure on the power sector and place more emphasis on the capital expenditures to accelerate economic growth in Nigeria through the manufacturing sector output and that government should also increase spending on road infrastructure, particularly on capital budgeting.

Eze (2014) examined the impact of fiscal policy on the manufacturing sector output in Nigeria, using Error Correction Model. The results of the study indicated that government expenditure significantly affect manufacturing sector output based on the magnitude and the level of significance of the coefficient and p-value and there is a long-run relationship between fiscal policy and manufacturing sector output. The study recommended expansionary fiscal policies for the growth of the manufacturing sector output in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical background of this paper is rooted in the Keynesian fiscal policy model. Following the 1929-30 Great Depression, the classical economists who opposed government interventions argued that strong trade unions prevented wage flexibility which resulted in high unemployment. The Keynesians, on the other hand, favoured government intervention to correct market failures. In 1936, John Maynard

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Keynes' (1883-1946) "General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money", criticized the classical economists for putting too much emphasis on the long run. According to Keynes, "we are all dead in the long run". Keynes believed depression needed government intervention as a short-term cure. Increasing savings will not help but spend. The government will increase public spending giving individuals, purchasing power and producers will produce more, creating more employment. This is the multiplier effect that shows causality from public expenditure to national income.

Keynes categorized public expenditure as an exogenous variable that can generate economic growth instead of an endogenous phenomenon. Hereby, Keynes believed the role of the government to be crucial as it can avoid depression by increasing aggregate demand and thus, switching on the economy again by the multiplier effect. It is a tool that brings stability in the short run but this needs to be done cautiously as too much public expenditure leads to inflationary situations while too little of it leads to unemployment. Therefore, the Keynesian model of government intervention revealed that there is a functional relationship between fiscal policy and industrial

$$MVA = \alpha + \beta_1 GNE + \beta_2 GTR + \beta_3 INT + \beta_4 REER + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where, MVA= Manufacturing value added, GNE = Gross National Expenditure, GTR= Government tax revenue, INT= Interest rate, and REER= Real effective exchange rate.

development through increased effective demand in the market. That is increased effective demand through increased government expenditure will therefore increase the level of industrial development in the economy. Thus, the Keynesian fiscal policy model served as theoretical framework for this paper, since it presents a framework that could be used to estimate the impact of fiscal policy on economic activity such as manufacturing sector performance.

This paper depended on secondary data sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, 2023 from 1986 to 2023. In this paper, the selected research design is the ex-post facto design. The ex-post facto design is particularly suited for studies aiming to decipher statistical associations between dependent and independent variables, primarily to establish cause-and-effect relationships.

Model Specification

The model for this paper is based on the theoretical framework and model that was adapted from the work of Muhammad *et al.* (2021) that examined the impact of fiscal policy on the performance of manufacturing sector in Nigeria from 1986 to 2017. The model applied in the study is of the form:

$$(1)$$

However, the above model was modified by including fiscal policy variables such as total government revenue, government recurrent and

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capital expenditures, and external debt. Thus, the modified model is presented as follows:

$$\ln MGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln GTREV_t + \beta_2 \ln GREXP_t + \beta_3 \ln GCEXP_t + \beta_4 \ln EXT D_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Where, In: Natural logarithm; MGDP = Manufacturing contribution to real gross domestic product, a proxy for manufacturing sector performance; GTREV = Government total tax revenue;

GREXP = Government recurrent expenditure; GCEXP = Government capital expenditure; EXT D = External debts. β_0 = The intercept or autonomous parameter estimate, β_1 to β_4 = Parameter estimate representing the coefficient

$$\Delta Y_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q \partial_j \Delta X_{t-j} + \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 X_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad (3)$$

Where Δ denotes the first difference operator, β_i , ∂_j , stand for the short-run coefficients, ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 are for the long-run coefficients and μ_t is the

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln MGDP_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_{1i} \ln MGDP_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^n \alpha_{2j} \Delta \ln GTREV_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^o \alpha_{3k} \Delta \ln GREXP_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^p \alpha_{4l} \Delta \ln GCEXP_{t-l} \\ & + \sum_{l=0}^r \alpha_{5l} \Delta \ln EXT D_{t-l} + \alpha_6 \ln MGDP_{t-1} + \alpha_7 \ln GTREV_{t-1} + \alpha_8 \ln GREXP_{t-1} + \alpha_9 \ln GCEXP_{t-1} + \alpha_{10} \ln EXT D_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The bounds test is conducted by testing the null hypothesis (H_0) against the alternative hypothesis (H_1) using the following equations:

$$H_0 : \alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha_3 = \alpha_4 = \alpha_5 = 0 \text{ and } H_1 : \alpha_1 \neq \alpha_2 \neq \alpha_3 \neq \alpha_4 \neq \alpha_5 \neq 0$$

The results of the bounds test derived from the computed F-Statistic are comparable to those of Pesaran *et al.* (2001), who concluded that

of GTREV, GREXP, GCEXP, and EXT D respectively, and ε_t - other variables not explicitly included in the model. It is expected that $\beta_1 - \beta_4 > 0$.

The paper investigated the impact of fiscal policy variables on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria fusing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) framework introduced by Pesaran *et al.* (2001). The ARDL model is specified as follows to run the bound test for cointegration:

disturbance(white noise) term. Transforming equation (2) into an ARDL Model results as follows:

cointegration between the series is present if the F-Statistic is greater than the upper bound I (1)

in each case, rejecting the null hypothesis of no cointegration.

$$\Delta \ln \text{MGDP}_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_{1i} \Delta \ln \text{MGDP}_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^n \alpha_{2j} \Delta \ln \text{GTREV}_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^o \alpha_{3k} \Delta \ln \text{GREXP}_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^p \alpha_{4l} \Delta \ln \text{GCEXP}_{t-l} + \sum_{l=0}^q \alpha_{5l} \Delta \ln \text{EXTD}_{t-l} + \text{ECT}_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \text{-----(5)}$$

Where,

ECT_{t-1} = lagged Error correction term. The output evolution process that agents use to react to the prior period of prediction errors is captured by the ECT.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique has an added advantage in the sense that it can be applied for any order of integration due to its dynamic nature. The ARDL method as suggested by Pesaran *et al.* (2001) can be adopted regardless of the integration order of

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the paper.

Table 1: Traditional Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Method	Level Stat. (Prob.)	First Diff. Stat. (Prob.)	Order of Integration
MGDP	ADF	-1.822331 (0.6729)	-4.542473*(0.0046)	I(1)
GTREV	ADF	-1.106565 (0.9143)	-4.868883*(0.0020)	I(1)
GREXP	ADF	-6.991815*(0.0000)	-8.336503*(0.0041)	I(0)
GCEXP	ADF	-2.208215 (0.9525)	-5.774432*(0.0031)	I(1)
EXTD	ADF	-6.429080*(0.0000)	-7.186321*(0.0000)	I(0)

Note: *, ** Indicates stationary at the 1% level.

Source: Researcher’s Computations using E-Views 12

From Table 1, government recurrent expenditure (GREXP) and External debts (EXTD) variables tends to be stationary at level

Mathematically, the series Error Correction Model with the ARDL framework is as follows:

the independent variables whether they are purely I (0), purely I (1) or mutually co-integrated (Gökmenoğlu & Taspinar, 2016; Katircioglu, 2009, 2010). The ARDL framework gives efficient results because it is free from serial correlation and endogeneity problems and can be estimated in the presence of endogenous explanatory variables (Pesaran *et al.*, 2001). The ARDL technique give more robust results for a small sample size than other conventional co-integration models.

according to the conventional test of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF). However, Real gross domestic product (MGDP);

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Government total tax revenue (GTREV); and Government capital expenditure (GCEXP) variables are likely to be stationary in first difference.

Co-integration Results

The variables were all found to be integrated at different orders; hence, they all satisfied the ARDL-bound testing approach which necessitates every variable in the equation to be static either at level or at first difference or modification. The essence of testing for the stationarity test or properties of the variables in bounds approach to co-integration is because the (ARDL) bounds test approach becomes applicable when variables integrated at level

Table 2: Result of ARDL Bounds Test for Cointegration

Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationships Exist		
Test Statistic	Value	K
F-Statistic	8.154775	4
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
5%	2.56	3.49

Source: Researcher's Computations based on E-Views 12

From Table 2, the bounds test value of the F-statistics which is 8.154775 is higher than the values of the upper and lower bound limit which are 2.56 and 3.49 at 5% critical level of significance. This means that there is a long run equilibrium relationship between the dependent variable and the explanatory variables of the model. Having established that there is a long run relationship between the variables, this

$I(0)$, first difference $I(1)$ or when they are mixed. This means that the assumption of bounds testing will collapse in the presence of $I(2)$ variable. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root results presented in Table 1, implies that the bounds testing approach is applicable in this study, as all the variables are a mixture of $I(1)$ and $I(0)$. The co-integration test helps to establish the existence of long run equilibrium relationships among variables of interest. If co-integration is found among variables, ARDL error correction model becomes applicable. The result of the cointegration test is presented in Table 2:

study proceeded to estimate the Error Correction Model.

Model Estimation Results

In light of the cointegration of the dependent variable with the regressors, the study proceeded to estimate the error correction and the long-term models. Table 3 presented the outcomes of the estimates as follows:

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Table 3: ARDL Regression Results
Dependent Variable: DLOG (MGDP)

Co-integrating Estimates (ECM Estimates)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DLOG(GTREV)	0.182648	0.035726	5.112454	0.0002
DLOG(GTREV(-1))	0.146920	0.035916	4.090610	0.0013
DLOG(GTREV(-2))	0.235330	0.035019	6.719990	0.0000
DLOG(GTREV(-3))	0.151815	0.037897	4.006004	0.0015
DLOG(GREXP)	-0.129000	0.039069	-3.301864	0.0057
DLOG(GREXP(-1))	-0.193942	0.040176	-4.827301	0.0003
DLOG(GREXP(-2))	-0.307770	0.054157	-5.682893	0.0001
DLOG(GREXP(-3))	-0.095730	0.049836	-1.920886	0.0769
DLOG(GCEXP)	0.029959	0.030400	0.985518	0.3424
DLOG(GCEXP(-1))	0.069592	0.029471	2.361359	0.0345
DLOG(GCEXP(-2))	-0.009963	0.028348	-0.351469	0.7309
DLOG(GCEXP(-3))	0.043059	0.028326	1.520112	0.1524
DLOG(EXTD)	0.094400	0.023344	4.043906	0.0014
DLOG(EXTD(-1))	0.085695	0.028244	3.034040	0.0096
DLOG(EXTD(-2))	0.104957	0.026460	3.966565	0.0016
CointEq(-1)*	-0.175394	0.021309	-8.230879	0.0000
R-squared	0.865745			
Adjusted R-squared	0.753866			
Durbin-Watson stat	1.602844			
Long Run				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOG(GTREV)	0.333672	0.698119	0.477959	0.6406
LOG(GREXP)	0.486745	0.356993	1.363458	0.1959
LOG(GCEXP)	-0.431347	0.296134	-1.456593	0.1690
LOG(EXTD)	-0.281399	0.232089	-1.212458	0.2469
C	6.892745	1.761392	3.913238	0.0018

Source: Researcher's Computation Using EViews-12 (2024)

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Based on Table 3, government total tax revenue, government recurrent expenditure at level, one period lagged government capital expenditure and external debts at level variables employed in this investigation has a statistically significant impact on manufacturing sector performance proxied by manufacturing contribution to real gross domestic product in the short-run. While, none of the variables has a statistically significant long-run impact on manufacturing sector performance. The estimated ARDL regression result indicated that government total tax revenue at level, one period lagged government capital expenditure and external debts at level variables are the main significant short-run drivers of manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria during this study period. While government total tax revenue, and government recurrent expenditure variables contributed positively to manufacturing sector performance in the long-run in Nigeria.

At the one percent level, the Error Correction Model is highly statistically significant,

Table 4: Diagnostic Test Results

Test	Null Hypothesis	T-Statistic	Prob
Jarque-Bera	There is a normal distribution	1.374	0.50
Heteroskedasticity: LM	No conditional heteroscedasticity	1.41	0.35
Heteroskedasticity: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	No conditional heteroscedasticity	0.903	0.59

Source: Researcher's Computations based on E-Views 12

negatively signed, and as expected. This provides more proof that the dependent variable and the regressors have a long-run relationship. The coefficient's absolute value, which falls between 0 and 1, shows that, in order to keep the equilibrium, yearly corrections are made to the short-run divergence from the equilibrium (long-run) position, which is roughly 18%. Since the explanatory variables account for more than 87% of the variation in manufacturing sector performance, the model appears to be well-fitting, as indicated by the R-squared value of 0.865745. On the other hand, the DW figure of 1.602844 indicated that there is no problem with serial correlation. As such, the conclusions of this study can be trusted for developing policy recommendations.

Post-Estimation Test Results

The study conducted a few diagnostic tests to assess the model's stability and applicability as well as the validity of the results. Results is as presented in Table 4 as follows:

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From Table 4, the model did not display serial correlation or heteroskedasticity during the study period. The heteroscedasticity tests indicated that the residuals are homoscedastic. The results of the diagnostic tests for serial correlation and heteroscedasticity suggested that the data is reasonably well behaved. Furthermore, the p-value for the normality test for the research period is greater than 0.05, indicating that the residues are distributed normally. This results in a uniform distribution of the residuals. As a result, the normal distribution null hypothesis was not rejected.

Figure 1: Stability Tests Result

Source: Researcher's Plot using E-Views 12

DISCUSSIONS

This paper examined the time series properties of the variables since the data used are of aggregate in nature. Thus, the variables were investigated for their stochastic properties using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit roots test. The unit root test results revealed that

Stability Test Result

The stability test in Figure 1 also revealed that the manufacturing sector performance model is stable during the study period as the plots of the charts lie within the critical bounds at 5% significant level. Bahmani-Oskooee and Rehman, (2005) noted that the null hypothesis that states the regression equation is correctly specified cannot be rejected when the plot of these statistics are within the critical boundaries at 5% significant level.

Government recurrent expenditure (GREXP) and External debts (EXTD) variables tends to be stationary at level. However, Real gross domestic product (MGDP); Government total tax revenue (GTREV); and Government capital expenditure (GCEXP) variables are likely to be stationary in first difference. Thereafter, to determine

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whether the relevant variables have a long-term relationship, the ARDL bounds test approach to co-integration was adopted and the result showed that the bounds test value of the F-statistics which is 8.154775 is higher than the values of the upper and lower bound limit which are 2.56 and 3.49 at 5% critical level of significance. This means that there is a long run equilibrium relationship between the dependent variable and the explanatory variables of the model. Having established that there is a long run relationship between the variables, this study proceeded to estimate the Error Correction Model.

From the estimated ARDL regression results in Table 3, government total tax revenue, government recurrent expenditure at level, one period lagged government capital expenditure and external debts at level variables employed in this investigation has a statistically significant impact on manufacturing sector performance in the short-run. While, none of the variables has a statistically significant long-run impact on manufacturing sector performance. The estimated ARDL regression result indicated that government total tax revenue at level, one period lagged government capital expenditure and external debts at level variables are the main significant short-run drivers of manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria during this study period. While government total tax revenue, and government recurrent expenditure variables

contributed positively to manufacturing sector performance in the long-run in Nigeria.

Furthermore, government total tax revenue, government capital expenditure and external debts at level variables are in agreement with this study apriori expectations in the short run. But government recurrent expenditure variable contradicts this study theoretical expectation in the short run. While, government total tax revenue, and government recurrent expenditure variables align with this study apriori expectations in the long run. However, government capital expenditure and external debts at level variables are not conformity with this study apriori expectations in in the long run. Further finding revealed that government tax revenue is positively and significantly related to manufacturing sector performance in the short-run. Consequently, one percentage increase in government total tax revenue will lead to an increase in manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria by 0.18 percent in the short run. This outcome is consistent with the a priori expectations of this investigation and prior studies such as Bolakale (2018), and Ezejiofor *et al.* (2015) who reported that tax revenue had significant and positive impact on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. Similarly, over the long term, the projected impact of government tax revenue on manufacturing sector performance is positive but statistically insignificant. Specifically, one percentage increase in government tax revenue

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will lead to an increase in manufacturing sector performance by 0.33% in the long-run.

On the other hand, the findings indicated that government recurrent expenditure appears to affect manufacturing sector performance negatively in the short-run. Controlling for other factors, for instance, a 1 percent increase in government recurrent expenditure will lead to a decrease in manufacturing sector performance by -0.13% in the short run. This outcome is inconsistent with the apriori expectations of the research and an indication that government recurrent expenditure is not contributing positively to manufacturing sector performance in the short-run. However, government recurrent expenditure is positively and insignificantly related to manufacturing sector performance in the long run. Specifically, one percentage increase in government recurrent expenditure will lead to an increase in manufacturing sector performance by approximately 0.49% in the long-run. This outcome is consistent with the apriori expectations of the research and studies such as Alozie (2021), Ubong and Ettah (2020) and Ubesie *et al.* (2020) whose findings confirmed that government recurrent expenditure contributes positively and has a considerable impact on manufacturing sector performance.

Furthermore, the estimated impact of one period lagged government capital expenditure on manufacturing sector performance in the short-run is positive and significant. By implication,

one percentage change or increase in one period lagged government capital expenditure will lead to 0.07% increase in manufacturing sector performance in the short-run. This outcome is consistent with the apriori expectations of this investigation, as government capital expenditure is expected to be directly related to manufacturing sector performance. This finding is in agreement with Effiong *et al.* (2024) who posited that capital expenditure exerted a positive and significant effect/ influence on manufacturing sector performance. While, government capital expenditure is insignificant and negatively related to manufacturing sector performance in the long run. Specifically, one percentage increase in government capital expenditure will lead to a decrease in manufacturing sector performance by approximately -0.43% in the long-run.

The coefficient of external debts at level is positive and significant in the short run. Consequently, if there is a 1% increase in external debts, it is predicted that there may be an increase of -0.09% in manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria in the short run. This outcome is consistent with the a priori expectations of this study. However, external debt is negative and insignificantly related to manufacturing sector performance in the long-run. This finding is in agreement with Joshua-Gyang (2024) who posited that public external debt in Nigeria have a negative effect on manufacturing industrial output.

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CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the impact of fiscal policy variables on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria from 1986 to 2023 using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Regression technique. Results revealed that government tax revenue is positively and significantly related to manufacturing sector performance in the short-run. Similarly, over the long term, the projected impact of government tax revenue on manufacturing sector performance is positive but statistically insignificant. On the other hand, the findings indicated that government recurrent expenditure appears to affect manufacturing sector performance negatively in the short-run. However, government recurrent expenditure is positively and insignificantly related to manufacturing sector performance in the long run. Furthermore, the estimated impact of one period lagged government capital expenditure on manufacturing sector performance in the short-run is positive and significant. While, government capital expenditure is insignificant and negatively related to manufacturing sector performance in the long run. While, the coefficient of external debts at level is positive and significant in the short run. However, external debt is negative and insignificantly related to manufacturing sector performance in the long-run. Therefore, the following recommendations were raised from the research findings.

- i. The Federal Ministry of Finance in collaboration with the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) should enhance efficiency in tax administration and widen the tax net to include the informal sector and digital economy, since a 1% increase in tax revenue led to a 0.18% rise in manufacturing sector performance in the short run.
- ii. The Budget Office of the Federation, and National Assembly Appropriations Committee should reallocate recurrent expenditure towards sectors that directly support the manufacturing sector (e.g., energy subsidies, transportation, R&D support), due to the negative impact of recurrent expenditure on manufacturing in the short-run.
- iii. The Federal Ministry of Works and Housing, and Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission (ICRC) should improve the planning, execution, and monitoring of capital projects, ensuring they target manufacturing-enabling infrastructure. This recommendation is apt due to the fact that lagged capital expenditure has a positive short-run impact (+0.07%), but negative long-run effects, likely due to delays, cost overruns, or misalignment.
- iv. The Debt Management Office (DMO), Ministry of Finance, National Assembly should limit unproductive external borrowing by tying new external borrowing strictly to capital projects that directly enhance industrial productivity (e.g., industrial parks, power

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generation), since external debt had positive impact in the short run but negative and insignificant impact in the long run on manufacturing sector performance.

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